

FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONALLY ORIENTED LANGUAGE COMPETENCE OF MEDICAL UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Annotation: this article presents an analysis of normative legal documents, scientific and pedagogical literature, the categorical apparatus of "professional competence", "language competence", the content of the concept of "professionally oriented language competence" is specified, the features of the formation of this competence are identified, the principles of professionally oriented learning are highlighted. The rapid development of medical science, the development and introduction of the latest technologies into clinical practice.

Key words: medical science, language competence, professional competence, competencies, foreign language.

To embark on, we should find out what is it competence? According to the definition of A.V. Khutorsky, competence is a person's readiness to mobilize knowledge, skills and external resources for effective activity in a specific life situation. Competence is a set of personal qualities of a student (value orientations, knowledge, skills, abilities), the ability to work in a certain personally significant area [5].

E.V. Lopanova by competencies means the characteristics of a specialist expressed through the ability to act, based on the unity of knowledge, professional experience and behavior, in accordance with the goal and the situation [4].

V.V. Laptev notes that competence can be defined as a complex (set) of knowledge, skills and abilities formed in the learning process, which makes up the content component of the training. Competence is a property of a personality, its ability to perform any activity based on the formed competence [3].

I.A. Zimnaya believes that competence is the possession of certain knowledge, skills and abilities that can be used in activities, and competence is a broader concept and is interpreted by the author as a knowledge-based intellectual and personality-driven socio-professional activity of a person. [1:]

The Council of Europe has adopted and defined the key competencies that future specialists should possess, and one of them is language competence, which allows significantly enriching the level of professional knowledge, skills and abilities by studying the achievements of science and practice, obtaining professional information from foreign sources.

According to the requirements of the Educational Standard of Higher Professional Education, to the structure of educational programs for training a specialist as a result of studying the discipline, the student should know: the main documents of international organizations, domestic and international professional medical associations, the principles of discussion, the main ways to solve problems and problems, basic medical and pharmaceutical terminology in Latin and foreign languages; possess a lexical minimum of 4000 educational lexical units; be able to: use at least 900 terminological units, evaluate and determine their needs necessary for continuing education; possess the skills of presenting an independent point of view, analysis and logical thinking. [7,8]

Currently, the purpose of studying the discipline "Foreign language" at a medical university is professionally oriented teaching of a foreign language to future doctors, the formation of the basics of foreign-language intercultural communication, mastering communication skills in a foreign language and using them as a means of information activity and further self-education [4]. A. Karandeeva believes that in the current situation, the training of specialists requires a radical changes in the strategy and tactics of training, when the main characteristic of a graduate of a medical university is his competence.

Teaching foreign language communication should be focused on the profile of the specialty on the basis of a competence-based approach aimed at developing students' ability to independently solve cognitive, communicative, organizational, professional tasks [6]. Therefore, taking into account the research results and the above-mentioned requirements prescribed in regulatory documents, it is necessary to organize the process of professionally oriented teaching of students a foreign language, the purpose of which in our study is the formation of professionally oriented language competence. In order to clarify the content of the concept of "professionally oriented language competence" and establish its links with professional competence (PC), language and communication competencies, we analyzed the scientific literature on these issues.

All of the above confirms the position that one of the main goals of higher professional training of a specialist in a non-linguistic university is the formation of his professionally oriented language competence.

However, despite a fairly large number of studies in domestic and foreign literature, it should be noted that modern foreign language teaching in a non-linguistic university, and in particular in a medical one, needs comprehensive improvement of methods, means, organization of practice-oriented training aimed at the formation of professionally oriented language competence, taking into account the constantly updated requirements of society, achievements of pedagogical and psychological sciences and its role as a tool for the formation of professional

competence and improving the quality of professional training, that is, the problem of the formation of professionally oriented language competence requires additional study.

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